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LONG TERM EARTH OBSERVATION MARKET DEVELOPMENT OF ENVISAT-BASED SERVICES

LINE 4: Environmental Information for Marine Operations

ENVISAT MONITORING AND FORECASTING SERVICES FOR OFFSHORE INDUSTRY (EMOFOR)

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Detailed Action Plan for integration of EO services into the MO portfolio

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by

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1. TARGET MARKET REQUIREMENTS

1.1 The EMOFOR Service Aims

Environmental conditions are of prime importance to the offshore industry, affecting many aspects of the development and operation of hydrocarbon-producing facilities. The EMOFOR project aims to provide the industry with an oceanographic monitoring and forecasting service that fully meets the needs of operational decision-makers. A clear understanding of those needs is therefore required, and the service must be tailored to ensure that it is (and remains) contemporary and relevant, and that it clearly communicates complex oceanographic scenarios to non-oceanographers. As discussed in the EO-Service Chain Definition document (D1), the emphasis of the Phase 1 service development is on floating offshore systems, such as those in use in the Gulf of Mexico, West Africa and offshore Brazil.

The geographical potential of the EMOFOR service and the nature of the oceanographic processes that it will address are described in detail in the EO-Service Chain Definition document (D1). In the current document some of the technical issues associated with developing the service are addressed, including what the industry would expect, interaction of the service chain elements and product delivery methods.

1.2 Summary of Requirements of the Offshore Industry

These topics are summarised here from the EO-Service Chain Definition document (D1):

- Geographical regions with major industry activity include Brazil, the Gulf of Mexico, Northwest Europe and West Africa. Secondary regions include Australia, the Caspian Sea, eastern Canada, the Arabian Gulf, India, the Mediterranean, Northwest Africa and the South China Sea.
- Sea ice coverage may be required in Alaska, eastern Canada, Sea of Okhotsk and the northern Caspian Sea.
- Oceanographic processes are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of main oceanographic processes and primary EMOFOR components

Region	Process/feature	Primary EMOFOR components
North Brazil/Trinidad	Retroreflection rings Vertical current shear Amazon outflow Solitons?	EO data; in-situ measurements Modelling; in-situ measurements In-situ measurements; EO data; modelling EO data; in-situ measurements
West Africa	Mesoscale eddies River inputs Inertial currents	EO data; modelling; in-situ measurements In-situ measurements; EO data; modelling In-situ measurements
Northwest Europe	Mesoscale eddies & meanders Slope current intensification	EO data; modelling; in-situ measurements Modelling; in-situ measurements
Gulf of Mexico	Loop Current eddies Near bed intensification	EO data; modelling; in-situ measurements In-situ measurements; modelling

	Sub-surface jets		In-situ measurements; modelling
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1.3 Scope of Opportunity for the EMOFOR Service

The breadth and diversity of activity within the offshore industry provides a range of opportunities for the EMOFOR service. The exploitation of an offshore hydrocarbon field comprises several key stages, as summarised in Figure 1 on the next page

Each stage has specific requirements for oceanographic information, which traditionally has been derived more from in-situ observations and/or models, but is increasingly utilising EO-based information. For example, the service will be attractive to those involved in towing and installation of offshore structures, who require a one-off bespoke product for a finite period of time. Equally, operators of facilities in regions such as the Gulf of Mexico, where severe currents are a regular occurrence, would benefit from regular monitoring and forecast reports throughout the duration of operations.

Many of the highly specialised offshore activities are sensitive to ocean currents at and below the sea surface. Accurate appraisal of environmental conditions is required in advance of some operations to minimise expensive downtime, and during others to ensure the safety of personnel and, increasingly, remotely-operated vehicles (ROV's). Table 2 gives a few example tasks and associated requirements for ocean current information that the EMOFOR service will provide.

Table 2. Example requirements for the EMOFOR service

Operational Phase	Task	Example EMOFOR requirements
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positioning • FPSO orientation • Subsea installation e.g. riser connection • Pipeline laying 	Mooring/anchor handling ROV/diver activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Up-to-date forecasts and real time monitoring of current speed and direction through water column; • Threshold exceedence stats.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Routine subsea intervention/maintenance • On-going hydrocarbon production 	ROV/diver activity Fatigue/load/VIV monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forecasts and real time monitoring of current speed and direction through water column. • Threshold exceedence stats.

ROV: Remotely-operated vehicle
 FPSO: Floating, Production Storage, Offloading vessel
 VIV: Vortex-induced vibration

For some operations, pre-planning is required to mitigate downtime due to adverse environmental conditions. Threshold analyses such as percentage exceedence and persistence are routinely used for this purpose and could be available through statistical manipulation of the EMOFOR input data.

A sample percentage exceedence presentation is shown in Table 2, giving the current speed percentage of occurrence above specified thresholds.

Figure 1. Lifecycle phases of an offshore development

Table 2. Sample current speed percentage exceedence statistics

1.4 Description of Floating Systems

As technology improves and hydrocarbon reserves in shallow water are depleted, exploration activities are moving into deeper water, with subsea equipment hundreds if not thousands of metres below the surface facilities. This has led to the development of floating production and storage units that are potentially more sensitive to environmental conditions than their fixed counterparts on the continental shelf. In deep water, exploration and appraisal drilling also is undertaken from floating platforms. Floating concepts fall into two general classes:

1. Monohull Floating, Production Storage and Offloading (FPSO) systems. Often converted tankers, these vessels are anchored to the seabed via a central turret connection that allows them to 'weathervane' in response to wind, waves and currents. The stored oil is transferred to shuttle tankers via pipelines connected to the rear of the vessel (see Figure 1, Production, for an example of the configuration). If rapid or severe changes in vessel orientation are not anticipated, breakage of hoses or connectors may occur. Subsea components of the system, such as the flexible risers and umbilicals, are susceptible to high loads caused by current flows over large portions of the water column and to sudden changes in flow direction.
2. Floating platform systems:
 - Semi-submersibles, used in both exploration/appraisal drilling and production stages. Semi-subs often have on-board propulsion systems (i.e. dynamic positioning), and advanced warning of potentially severe current conditions is required when positioning.
 - Spar systems. Spars consist of a deep-draught, vertical, cylindrical hull with a deck mounted on the top. They are moored in deepwater by taut moorings that reduce motion of the hull caused by near-surface conditions. Due to their deep draught, current profile information is required to monitor loads.
 - Tension-Leg platforms (TLPs). Configurations include a single surface-piercing column with three radial pontoons, from which tensioned moorings anchor the platform to the seabed. TLPs are susceptible to strong currents throughout the water column.

1.5 Service Performance Requirements

For the EMOFOR service to be recognised by the oil and gas industry as an indispensable decision-making tool, there are a range of criteria it must meet. At this stage of the service development the means of addressing these conditions are still conceptual, and are discussed in later sections of this report.

- **Reliability:** The service **must** be delivered regularly and on time. Environmental conditions in dynamically active regions often change rapidly and hence the information delivered within the service must be up-to-date. An illustration of this occurred recently when a Fugro GEOS real-time current measurement system aboard a rig in the Faroe-Shetland Channel (north-west Scotland) recorded a sudden sustained increase in surface current speed to nearly 1.5 ms^{-1} , together with a co-incident drop in temperature of more than 1°C . The operators needed to know quickly how long this would last as it represented a potential hazard to their subsea operations. Timely EMOFOR products would have forecast the event, enabled an estimate of its likely duration and identified the cause and perhaps the likelihood of re-occurrence.

Accuracy: Confidence in the service will depend upon the accuracy of the products. The service must make realistic estimates of present and future conditions. As with weather forecasting, if there is no skill then the service will fail. Precise estimates are not critical for most operational activities, though it would be essential for use in hindcast mode.

- **Flexibility:** The EMOFOR service chain must be sufficiently flexible to deal with ad-hoc requests for information made in response to operational needs or rapidly changing conditions.
- **Expandability:** The service must be configured such that users in new geographical regions may be easily accommodated. The service chain must also be capable of simultaneously servicing many clients in a range of locations.
- **Communication:** the service product must be easily communicable to offshore personnel as well as those in land-based offices. This may have implications on the amount of information that the product can contain.
- **Presentation:** The service will necessarily describe complex oceanographic scenarios to non-oceanographers and the product must therefore be tailored to meet the needs of non-experts. This has direct implications for the means by which the service product is delivered to the client.
- **Cost:** The service must appear cost-effective to the customer.

1.6 Proposed solution: integrated service system

The integrated service system, proposed to be developed for the offshore market, was described in D1 where the different components of the service chain were briefly discussed. The modules of existing services and how these services can be integrated into an overall monitoring and forecasting system was also described. In this report the different modules are analysed in more detail.

Currently EO data services regularly provide sea surface data with reasonable resolution, such as sea surface temperature, sea level anomalies, surface waves and other variables. However, oceanographic services needed for offshore activities also require estimates of subsurface and deep water conditions. For example, one important key parameter is the three dimensional current velocity field. To meet the need for three dimensional data, an overall integrated system is proposed which includes use of:

- high resolution sea surface information from satellite remote sensing (EO data)
- in situ measurements (for current measurements, wave measurements, etc.)
- three dimensional oceanographic fields from ocean circulation models

Furthermore, the service system should be capable of operating in different modes:

- (1) Hindcast mode: long time series for statistical analysis purposes;
- (2) Real time or nowcast mode;
- (3) Forecast mode.

This report will describe the service elements and outline an implementation plan of an integrated ocean monitoring and forecasting service system for offshore operations exploiting EO-data, *in situ* measurements, and state-of-the-art ocean modeling systems with advanced assimilation schemes.

2. SERVICE INTEGRATION REQUIREMENTS

2.1 Technical requirements

2.1.1 Delivery Options

As suggested in Chapter 1 of this document, the architecture of the EMOFOR service must be flexible and easy for non-oceanographers to use and understand. The Internet offers an ideal platform from which to host the service, and at the EMOFOR meeting of 19th March 2002 two potential service delivery routes were identified:

1. Fugro GEOS operates METNET, an intranet/internet-based system that collates and displays in real-time a range of metocean parameters measured aboard Shell's North Sea platforms (Figure 3 and 4 shows sample screens). Although METNET is proprietary to Shell (the web-sites it uses are secure and are maintained by Fugro GEOS), the concept could be adapted for use in the EMORFOR service and be expanded to accommodate data from NERSC and CLS. A similar system is in operation in the South China Sea.

Figure 3. Sample METNET display showing the home page of Shell Expro

Figure 4. Sample METNET displays showing present met-ocean conditions at one of the offshore sites

A disadvantage of this concept is that it is geared towards sending data from offshore, rather than from onshore to the offshore facilities. Whilst offering the necessary flexibility, the development work required for each new client may render the concept cost-ineffective for short-term or one-off service subscribers.

2. The second approach is a web-based application allowing the user to log onto a password-protected Internet site to download the EMOFOR products. The project partners all have experience delivering web-based oceanographic information (see the EO Service Chain Definition Document, D1, for details) and hence this route is preferable; it is also more flexible and is relatively straightforward to implement. The concept is discussed and developed in more detail in the following sections of this chapter.

2.1.2 Internet Service Delivery

If the Internet delivery chain were selected by the project partners as the most appropriate option, the flow of data from providers to client users would be as depicted in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Internet service chain

EO products from CLS and in-situ measurements from Fugro GEOS would continue to be assimilated by NERSC into their models (see also Figure 1 of the EO Service Chain Definition Document). However, all partners would also make their products available via secure FTP site to

Fugro GEOS who, as MO (market owner), would upload the required information on a regular basis, nominally weekly, for storage in a central data digital 'warehouse'. It may be possible to automate this activity, which would then be reliant on the data providers routinely populating their respective FTP sites. The model and satellite information would be stored in a central database (warehouse) within the Fugro GEOS network, along with the in-situ current measurements (note that developments are currently underway to enable rig-based ADCP measurements to be telemetered onshore in real-time via satellite). The data would therefore be subject to the provisions already in place to protect confidentiality and integrity. Fugro GEOS has extensive experience in data warehousing and hence development of the EMOFOR warehouse is not anticipated to be especially onerous. It would, however, require detailed discussion with NERSC and CLS to ensure that the Fugro GEOS architecture is compatible with the formats of the model and EO data (see EMOFOR EO Service Chain Definition document D1 for a preliminary description of the products proposed by the data providers). The concept of a central warehouse facilitates the production of routine reports and forecasts, possibly automatically, whilst also allowing user intervention to deal with ad-hoc specialised requests, for example the development of design criteria.

Fugro GEOS is currently conducting a major re-development of its scientific software, with the intention of pooling all oceanographic analysis and reporting tasks under a single, advanced suite of tools. Extension of this suite specifically for the project will probably be more efficient and cost effective and a scope of work will be finalised once the project partners have defined the service products in more detail. For some service requests, it may be necessary to by-pass the delivery chain and take products directly from CLS and/or NERSC.

2.1.3 Presentation Methods

1. The advantage of an internet-based approach is that service flexibility and usability are maximised and a wide range of user requirements is catered for. There are several means by which the service can be implemented for a given client, depending on the individual set of circumstances: For multi-rig operations, whilst each facility would have interest only in local conditions, a central shore-based controller could have access to all rig web-sites. In such cases, the level of service required might be defined by the operating company and the same products would be delivered to each offshore facility. Depending on the Client's policy, either individual rigs or shore-based personnel could contact Fugro GEOS for additional service products. This approach potentially would enable operator collectives to pool information and to observe certain dynamic features (e.g. eddies) in advance at upstream monitoring facilities. This would, however, raise commercial issues of access to other parties' data.
2. Timed delivery: a standard forecast report is made available on a password-protected web site at pre-determined times. The user simply logs onto the site and downloads the latest report in pdf format, which is the last in a list of previous forecasts. This is the simplest delivery method, but is relatively inflexible, although a series of report options of differing levels of detail or with different emphasis could be made available. This style of service is currently offered by Fugro

GEOS in the Trinidad Ring Advisory Co-operative (TRAC), which provides weekly updates of the movement of large eddies off the northern coast of Brazil based on altimetry and surface drifter trajectories. Email reminders containing a brief summary of the new nowcast/forecast may be advisable so that the clients are aware of updates as soon as possible.

3. On demand service: on an as-required basis the user sends an email to a unique Fugro GEOS address, or telephones Fugro GEOS, giving details of the location and required information (from a pre-defined list of service options or presentations). The selected presentations are then extracted from the data warehouse and placed on the password-protected web-site or emailed back to the user. This system is currently in use by Fugro GEOS for providing members of the North West Approaches Group of oil companies with model data produced by NERSC. Figure 6 shows sample pages from the web-site.

Figure 6. The user interface for Fugro GEOS' on-demand service.

Enabling a choice of presentation options would give the user a degree of control over the service for which he is paying. The level of technical detail provided would be automatically commensurate with his oceanographic knowledge. Similar systems are operated by CLS (CATSAT) and by Fugro GEOS' marine weather forecasting services (Figure 7), although with the former special software is required aboard the receiving vessel to display and interact with the downloaded maps.

Figure 7. Fugro GEOS' weather forecasting user interface

Fugro GEOS marine weather forecasters operate a round-the-clock service to respond to telephone and email requests for forecasts. Although a standard report is generally the default, the forecasters are able to provide a range of other, more tailored products. If the request is the first from a user, he will be given a user name and password that will enable him to log in to the web site and download his forecasts when they are ready. The forecasters offer expert technical support during critical operations, a facility that is also anticipated in the EMOFOR service.

2.2 Blockages in use of EO data and plan to overcome the blockages

The use of EO data in met-ocean services for the offshore industry started fairly recently and there is a number of blockages which currently restrict the use of such data. A list of known blockages and mitigation plan to overcome the blockages is given in Table 3. Additional blockages, which we presently do not know, may also arise during the development of the EMOFOR Service.

Table 3. Plan to overcome blockages in use of EO data

<i>Blockages</i>	<i>Mitigation action</i>
1. No dedicated service to provide ocean current information to the offshore industry have yet been established. The market is therefore not used to apply EO-information in a systematic way, and there is skepticism towards new methods where the cost-benefit is not proven	The idea behind to EMOFOR service components is to introduce new EO products as part of the existing services that Fugro GEOS is providing to the market. EO products will not be delivered alone, but as part of a total service which includes use of in situ data and modelling
2. Products from EO data do not measure quantitatively the current parameters which are required. Most of the products provide indirect information or qualitative information on current parameters. This means that EO data cannot replace in situ measurements, but serve as an additional source of information.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide quantitative SST and SLA fields which can be used in modelling as well as in direct monitoring. • Provide qualitative products from EO data such as eddy tracking in near real time and current statistics from altimetry
3. Presently, many different EO products for the marine environment are available from several service providers, but the access to the products can be cumbersome	Dedicated products for the offshore industry will be made available from a single server (the Data Warehouse of Fugro GEOS)
4. EO –derived products used alone can be useful in some situations (i.e. for eddy tracking), but the EO-products are more useful in combination with in situ data and modelling	The EMOFOR service concept is based on integrated use of EO data, in situ data and modelling
5 Presentation of EO-information is not well adapted to a given category of users	Presentation of information from different sources will be done in a way which is

	optimised for the users.
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Table 3 (cont.)

6. EO information is provided by several satellites and the customers need to have service providers which can deliver a final product which combines data from several satellites	CLS is developing services which integrate EO data from several satellites Fugro GEOS will deliver an integrated service which includes EO data, in situ data and modelling.
7. Temporal and spatial coverage of existing satellite data is not sufficient for many marine processes.	Use of data from several satellites will improve the coverage. Especially ENVISAT data will make important contribution to better coverage.
8. The detection capability of eddies is limited for existing EO sensors.	ENVISAT which provides simultaneous coverage by MERIS, AATSR and ASAR will improve the detection capability
9. Cost of using EO data, especially SAR data, is a limiting factor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the service will use synergy of altimeter, optical, IR and SAR data for eddy tracking, where SAR data is used only when the other data source are not useful (i.e during cloud conditions and for tracking smaller eddies) • SAR price policy for commercial users needs to be reviewed
10. Promotion and marketing of new EO products to the offshore industry needs to be strengthened	Service test trials to be demonstrated and other marketing activities will done be in Phase 2 of EMOFOR

3. PLAN FOR SERVICES USING EO DATA

3.1 Eddy mapping and tracking with EO data

Active components of the service chain in the case of eddy mapping and tracking with EO data are shown in Fig. 11. Altimeter data can deliver maps of sea level anomalies which indicate position, size and intensity of an eddy, while images from SAR, optical and infrared images give instantaneous location and size of an eddy at given time intervals for example 3 days.

Figure 11. Active components of the service chain in case of eddy mapping. In situ current measurements are supporting data to validate the observations from EO data.

3.1.1 Products from radar altimeter data

For several years, CLS (Collecte Localisation Satellite: <http://www.cls.fr>) and CCAR (Colorado Center for Astroynamics Research: <http://www-ccar.colorado.edu>) produce maps of Sea Level Anomalies (SLA) in Near Real Time (NRT). Note that by NRT, we mean delays of about 1 to 2 days. At present these maps, which show the circulation pattern of mesoscale eddies, are based on data from the radar altimeters onboard TOPEX/Poséidon and now JASON (U.S.-French satellite), ERS-2 (European satellite) and GFO (U.S satellite). In the near future, these maps will take into

account the data extracted from radar altimeters onboard ENVISAT (European satellite). An overview of the altimeter satellites to be used in EMOFOR is given in Table 5. Altimeter data are independent of cloud and light conditions and SLA maps can be used to monitor eddies of order 100 km and which propagate slowly (0.10 m/s). This is typical for eddies at lower latitudes such as in Gulf of Mexico and off the coast of Brazil (Fig.12). Because the temporal and spatial resolution of altimeter-derived SLA maps is relatively coarse, the SLA maps are less feasible to monitor small scale eddies (order 10- 30 km) which propagate rapidly (0.5 m/s), such as eddies in the North-Atlantic Current

Table 5. Satellite used by CCAR and CLS processing systems

Satellite	T/P	ERS-2	GFO	Jason	ENVISAT
Country	USA/France	Europe	USA	USA/France	Europe
User	NASA, JPL, CNES	ESA	US Navy	NASA, JPL, CNES	ESA
Size	~10 m long	~11 m long	~3 m long	~3 m long	26 m long
Mass	2442 kg	2516 kg	300 kg	500 kg	8211 kg
Date launch	10 Aug 1992	21 Apr 1995	10 Feb 1998	7 Dec 2001	1 Mar 2002
Orbit altitude	1336 km	800 km	880 km	1336 km	800 km
Inclination	66°	98.5°	108°	66°	98.5°
Repeat period	10 days	35 days	17 days	10 days	35 days

In order to map the ocean surface variability with sufficient temporal and spatial sampling, a least 2 (and preferably 3 or 4) altimeters are needed. CLS has demonstrated that simultaneous use of TOPEX/POSEIDON (T/P) and ERS1/2 can be successfully used to map SLA with typical time interval of 10 days. CLS is developing a completely new upgraded version of the DUACS data merging software that will operate under UNIX to become fully operational in the ENVISAT-JASON period. The main output of this software will thus be high-quality sea level anomalies (SLA), either along the satellite tracks or mapped on a regular grid (MSLA). Nominal operating frequency is once per week but one can envision a higher data production frequency. ENVISAT RA-2 will replace ERS altimeter and in combination with Jason (to replace T/P) and Geosat Follow-On the altimeter coverage and repeat cycles will be optimum for monitoring of the sea surface height variability associated with mesoscale and large scale time dependent ocean circulation features.

Tools for eddy mapping and tracking service will be developed by CLS using high-frequency altimeter data mapping combined with sea surface temperature and ocean colour maps. This tools will be based on eddy and front detection methodology presently being studied at CLS. This service will be tested for the different areas of the study regions.

TOPEX/ERS-2 Analysis May 18 1999

Figure 12. a) Example of combined TOPEX/ERS-2 SLA map produced by CCAR covering the North Brazil Current, b) Similar product but only SLA data from selected orbits are plotted, covering a specific eddy.

3.1.2 Products from SAR, optical and infrared images

Imaging data from SAR optical and infrared satellite sensors can play an important complementary role to altimeter data for eddy mapping and tracking. Image data products include: 1) SAR images showing contrast in surface roughness associated with current gradients in an eddy; 2) ocean colour contrast images from optical sensors, and 3) sea surface temperature maps from infrared radiometers which identifies eddies in cases where there is a temperature gradient between the eddy and the surrounding water masses. Examples of use of these imaging data for eddy tracking are shown in Fig. 13.

Figure 13. Examples of eddy observations off the west coast of Norway by three types of satellite imaging instruments: a) SAR image from ERS-2, showing three eddies (A and B are cyclonic, while B is anticyclonic) in an area where in situ data from current meter moorings verified the eddies (indicated by the red arrows); b) ocean colour map indicating chlorophyll concentration (red is high and blue is low concentration) from SeaWiFS data; and c) Surface temperature from NOAA AVHRR (red is warm and blue is cold water).

There are currently many imaging sensors on operating satellites, with spectral response from visual through near-infrared and thermal infrared to microwaves. They can be classified in four categories:

- 1) High-resolution image (<100m) optical sensors (radiometers)
- 2) Medium resolution image (200 - 1000m) optical sensors (radiometers)
- 3) Synthetic aperture microwave imaging radar (SAR)
- 4) Low resolution image (10 -50km) microwave sensors (radiometers).

For mapping and monitoring of current-related signatures categories 2) and 3) are mostly used, due to adequate spatial-temporal coverage of the target area. High resolution optical sensors (category 1) have a narrower, (but often steerable) swath, are also useful but the cost-benefit is less due to the required data coverage. Category 4 has very wide swaths, but generally too coarse a resolution for most ocean and coastal mapping purposes. The categories are specified in Table 6.

Table 6. SAR, optical and infrared satellite sensors in operation

Sensor type	Pixel size	Swath width	Satellite sensors in operation
1. High resolution optical sensors (radiometers)	< 100 m	60 – 190 km	HRV on SPOT-4/5 ETM on Landsat- 7 ASTER on Terra (EOS)
2. Medium resolution optical sensors (radiometers)	200 – 1000 m	500 – 2500 km	AVHRR on NOAA-14/15/16 AATSR on Envisat MERIS on Envisat MODIS on Terra and Aqua (EOS) VEGETATION on SPOT 4/5 SeaWiFS on OrbView-2
3. Synthetic aperture microwave imaging radar (SAR).	30 – 200 m *	100 – 500 km	SAR on ERS-2 ScanSAR on Radarsat-1 ASAR on Envisat
4. Low resolution passive microwave imaging sensors	10 50 km	> 1000 km	SSM/I on DMSP F-13/14/15 AMSR/E on Aqua (EOS)

* Depending on noise reduction

Production, analysis and delivery of images for eddy tracking will be a joint effort by NERSC and CLS, where NERSC will be responsible for the SAR data and CLS for the optical and infrared images. CLS envisions up a service chain where products from ENVISAT MERIS and AATSR data, supported by other similar satellite instruments (NOAA-AVHRR and SPOT-VGT), will be delivered. NERSC is preparing a scheme for eddy tracking using ENVISAT ASAR in near real time from ground stations covering the service area. The scheme for a SAR eddy tracking service has previously been set up for ERS data and will be adapted to ENVISAT ASAR data as soon as these data become available from ESA. Fig. 14 shows how the integration of the different products from CLS and NERSC will be implemented as part of the Fugro GEOS service system. As examples of what ENVISAT can deliver, image data from ERS/RADARSAT (SAR), SeaWiFS (optical) and AVHRR (IR data) have been prepared for use for the eddy tracking service, as shown in Fig 13. Another example of SAR eddy detection is shown in Fig. 15.

The integration of EO-products from several sensors and the role of the partners in the service chain are shown in Fig. 14.

With ENVISAT imaging instruments (ASAR, MERIS and AATSR) combined with RA-2, it is envisaged that the eddy tracking capability implemented in worldwide services will be significantly improved. The most important improvements to be expected from ENVISAT are:

- ENVISAT will add observing capabilities to other existing and planned EO satellites, resulting in more frequent observations which is necessary for an eddy tracking service;
- Simultaneous observation of the sea surface by ASAR, MERIS and partly AATSR which increases the the probability of detecting eddies and current structures under different met-ocean conditions;
- Ability to cover larger areas with ASAR Wide Swath, facilitating the localisation of eddies upstream of the operation site in areas of frequent cloud cover;
- Increased revisit time of ASAR, which makes it possible to have observations every two days at 70 N and every 3 days at 60 N;
- Possibility to select between VV and HH polarisation and incidence angle from 15 degrees to 45 degrees, which can improve the capability to detect eddies and other surface features;
- In cloudless areas, MERIS and AATSR can be used alone to detect eddies, with the advantage of wider swaths;
- On-board storage of ASAR data, which makes it possible to obtain data outside the station mask of existing ground stations.

Figure 14. Outline of service chain for ENVISAT data products delivered by CLS and NERSC to Fugro GEOS Data Warehouse from which the customers can request data products.

Figure 15. Example of eddy detection with SAR from ERS-2 on 11 June 1997 at the Ormen Lange field west of Mid-Norway. A well-defined cyclonic eddy is seen southwest of the three Ormen Lange current meter moorings (OL1, OL2 and OL3). In this area, OL1 measured 15 cm/s in direction 0° , OL2 measured 40 cm/s in direction 350° , and OL3 measured 40 cm/s in direction 330° (indicated by red arrows). These directions are all in good agreement with the line features defining the eddy (yellow circle and arrows).

The value-adding attributes of ENVISAT data in the service modes and service scenarios are reviewed in Table 7, which shows that ENVISAT will play a role in the service modes and the proposed service scenarios. In the weekly SST and SLA field, ENVISAT is one of several satellites, which provide data for the production of fields.

Table 7. Contribution of ENVISAT data in the planned service modes and service scenarios

Proposed service scenarios	Components of a 3-D service system			Service modes		
	2-D sea surface maps from EO data	In situ data: surface and vertical profile	3-D ocean field from models	Monitoring (real time)	Hindcast (analysis of time series)	Forecasting (1 Ğ 7 days)
1 Eddy mapping and tracking with EO data	ASAR, MERIS, RA-2, AATSR			Maps: 3 Ğ 7 days updating		
2 Eddy statistics from altimeter hindcast data	RA-2 + previous RA data			10 daily maps of eddy kinetic energy	Eddy kin. energy time series of several years	
3 Statistics from model hindcast data			Weekly SLA and SST fields		Validation of model performance	
4 Forecasting from models			Assimilation of SLA and SST fields			Improved forecasting

The data coverage of the ENVISAT sensors (Fig. 16 a) shows that ASAR wide swath images (400 km wide) will have complete coverage at latitudes above 60° N every 3 days. Further south the coverage will be reduced. The SAR coverage can be improved by using both ascending and descending passes, and by supplementing it with RADARSAT images.

ASAR wide swath images will overlap with parts of the MERIS swath (1150 km wide) almost completely, the AATSR coverage is totally within the MERIS swath, while ASAR only overlaps with AATSR for the innermost narrow mode swath (Fig. 16 b)

Wide Swath coverage
3 days
35-day repeat cycle [501 orbits]; Reference: 0.133500 deg. orbit 1; First orbit 1, Last orbit 43

a)

b)

Figure 16. a) Coverage over 3 days by ASAR Wideswath mode at medium and high latitudes; b) Overlap of MERIS, AATSR and ASAR modes in the same orbit.

3.1.3 Technical summary of eddy mapping service

The technical status of the eddy mapping products is summarized in Table 8.

Table 8. Summary of eddy mapping service elements

Service elements	Integrated product: Eddy maps			
	Altimeter SLA maps	SAR eddy maps	IR maps	Optical maps
Responsible institution	CLS	NERSC	CLS	CLS
Production chain established	yes	Yes, for data in Northern Europe	Yes, with AVHRR data	Yes, with VGT data
Example of products presented in the report	Fig. 12 a and b	Fig. 13 a	Fig. 13 c	Fig. 13 b
Inclusion of ENVISAT data	when RA-2 data is available	when ASAR data is available	when AATSR data is available	when MERIS data is available
Geographical coverage	Regional products from global data	Within SAR ground stations	Regional products from global data	Regional products from global data
Near real time delivery (from time of product generation)	Within 1 – 2 days	Within 1 day	Within 1-2 days	Within 1-2 days
Product interval	Every week	Every 3 – 6 days	Every 3 – 4 days	Every 3 – 4 days
Time averaged products	Averaged over 10 days	Instant image	Averaged over 3 – 4 days	Averaged over 3 – 4 days
Product format	A standard format for raster files	A standard format for raster files	A standard format for raster files	A standard format for raster files
Delivery of product to FG	By ftp to Data Warehouse	By ftp to Data Warehouse	By ftp to Data Warehouse	By ftp to Data Warehouse
Reliability of product access	Good: because data comes from min. 2 satellites,	Good in regions covered by SAR receiving stations	Good: because of ENVISAT product distribution policy for AATSR	Good: because ENVISAT product distribution policy for MERIS-RR
Limiting factors of the EO product	Mapping of small and rapidly moving eddies is not feasible	Dependent on wind conditions	Dependent on cloud conditions	Dependent on cloud conditions
Have products been used or tested by FG before ?	yes	no	yes	yes
Have products been used or tested by end users before ?	yes	yes	yes	yes
Access to service	Direct link to be established between CLS and FG	Direct link from NERSC to FG	Direct link to be established between CLS and FG	Direct link to be established between CLS and FG
Plan for service trial in Phase 2	In Northwest Europe and in Gulf of Mexico (see description in chapter 6)			
Validation of products	Validation of the overall eddy maps will be done during the service trials, mainly by comparison with in situ current measurements.			
Integration of products in a service	FG will do integration of the products as part of their services to the offshore industry. Note that mapping of eddies does not need to use all the four input products simultaneously. FG will select the best of the four input products, depending on its quality, every time eddy information is to be sent to the customers			

7 averaged maps over 7 – 10 days are produced for input to models and for monitoring in areas where eddies are changing more slowly

3.1.4 Actions to be done before the service trials

Data access

The SAR service chain has until now only been tested with SAR data from ERS and RADARSAT. Ordering, acquisition and analysis of ASAR data for the required modes in near real-time will be tested within the area covered by Tromsø Satellite Station as soon as ASAR data can be obtained in this area. The service trial demonstration will be carried out in the European Atlantic Margin, which is covered by Tromsø Satellite Station and in the Gulf of Mexico. SAR data acquisition for Gulf of Mexico need to be prepared. Ordering, acquisition and delivery of MERIS (level 2RR) and AATSR level 2 products (ATS_NR_2P) in near real time in the service trial areas need to be tested to find typical time delay and access to required data products. Action: NERSC and CLS.

Determine the cost of using altimeter, SAR, optical and infrared images in the service

The price of using the EO data for the service trials will be negotiated with the data providers.

Integration of information from altimeter, SAR, optical and infrared images

Since each of the input products have limitations, which inhibit retrieval of eddy information under given conditions, the service will extract the best products for each day. Combination of information will be done if several input products contribute to eddy mapping. FG using GIS methods will do this. The overall quality of the eddy maps should therefore be better than each of the input products.

Quality of products

The overall quality of eddy mapping needs to be tested, and this will be done as part of the service trials. The first testing of eddy mapping capability will be done in Phase 1 as soon as ASAR, MERIS and AATSR data can be acquired over one of the trail areas. Quality assessment will be done jointly by FG, NERSC and CLS.

Test throughput capacity

It will be important to ensure that the service can deliver products in near real time, which is currently defined to be within 1 day (24 hours). The amount of data to be processed is fairly limited; each trial area will require processing and analysis of typical one ASAR, one MERIS and one AATSR image per day. In addition there will be similar amount of data from other satellites. Action: NERSC and CLS.

Data Warehouse at Fugro GEOS

Fugro GEOS is developing its Data Warehouse, and before the service trials can be implemented the Data Warehouse will be developed to a stage where it can be used to integrate, present and submit information products to selected customers.

Select a customer for each service trial

A customer of Fugro GEOS will be contacted and asked to evaluate and assess the service trials and give recommendations for improvement and further development

Delivery to customers

Prepare distribution of products from the service trials to the selected customer from the Data Warehouse via web and/or by human interaction.

3.2 Eddy statistics from altimeter hindcast data

3.2.1 Products on eddy statistics from altimeter data

When time series of SLA fields from altimeter data have obtained over many years, it is feasible to calculate a variable called Eddy Kinetic Energy which is of relevance as historical statistical information supplementing time series of oceanographic current measurements. Maps of Eddy Kinetic Energy is proposed as a product in the Hindcast mode of the services which the industry can use in Exploration/Appraisal phase as well as in the Design phase of an offshore development. Only altimeter processing is active in the processing chain (Fig. 17), while time series of in situ data can be used as validation data if available. The advantage of using altimeter data to estimate eddy statistics is that global data sets are available and can be used at very low cost to plan operations in new regions before deployment of in situ measurement systems. Also the amount of altimeter data is growing due to new satellites with radar altimeters, which will lead to improved statistical estimates.

Figure 17. Active components of the service chain in the case of providing eddy kinetic energy.

Since 1998 CLS has produced historical altimetric maps, such as eddy kinetic energy, based on TOPEX/POSEIDON, ERS-1/2 and Geosat Follow-On. A combination of data from several satellites is necessary to improve the spatial and temporal resolution of the maps. Example of altimeter grid for Northwest Europe based on TOPEX/POSEIDON and ERS-1/2 data is shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18. Mean Topex/Poseidon tracks (black) and ERS-1/2 tracks (Red) superimposed on the bathymetry of the area where the North-Atlantic Current enters the Norwegian Sea.

The maps of Eddy Kinetic Energy are derived from the mapped geostrophic velocity anomaly data in the following way: Eddy kinetic energy at each grid point is calculated as the sum of squares of the magnitude of the velocity anomaly ($1/2 \langle uu \rangle$, where $\langle uu \rangle$ is the RMS of geostrophic velocity normal to the passes over a certain time period) and plotted as a contour plot showing the distribution of this temporally averaged parameter in space. The maps give a good quantitative estimate of the magnitude of the mesoscale variability and identify locations where it is higher than the nominal values. An example of seasonal eddy kinetic energy maps averaged over several years for the study area indicated in Fig 18 is shown in Fig. 19. Comparison of the seasonal eddy kinetic energy between the winter months of 1994 and 1995 is shown in Fig. 20, zooming in on the Faroe Island – Shetland area.

Figure 19. Seasonal eddy kinetic energy (cm^2s^{-2}) in Northwest Europe averaged for 1993-1998.

Figure 20. Seasonal eddy kinetic energy (EKE) for January-March for 1994 (a) and 1995 (b) in the Faroe Islands - Shetland region. High EKE (red-yellow-green) is found in the inflow region for the North Atlantic Current.

The EKE distribution provides an indication of areas with enhanced mesoscale activity, in the form of eddies, fronts, meandering currents as well as variations in the strengths of the current. The plots show high EKE (above $100 \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-2}$) along the path of the Norwegian Atlantic Current, with highest values (up to $200 \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-2}$ seen within the Faroe-Shetland Channel. This is to be expected, as mesoscale activity is generally higher in the neighbourhood of strong currents, which often interact with the topography to generate meanders and eddies. In the Norwegian Sea, there are pockets of high EKE in the area of Ormen Lange where deep sea development is in progress (Fig. 19). EKE is low over most of the deep basin of the Norwegian Sea and in the northern reaches of the North Sea. The data also reveal significant seasonal variability in the EKE distributions. There is a tendency for enhanced activity over large parts of the study area in the winter season (October-March) compared to the summer season (April-September).

3.2.2 *Service chain for historical altimetry maps*

Analysis of EKE from historical altimetric data for a given geographical area will be proposed for customers planning deep sea development in new areas as part of the general oceanographical investigation and prior to/during deployment of current meter moorings. Upon request from customers, the analysis will start and results provided according to the following steps carried out by CLS:

- Remove orbit error: Global cross over minimisation using the more accurate T/P altimeter data as the reference to reduce ERS-1/2 orbit error.
- Creation of SLA: Relative to a 3 year mean profile, consistent for T/P and ERS.
- Filtering of SLA: Using a Loess filter to remove high frequency signal over 63 km for along track calculation of geostrophic velocities, over 35 kilometres to smooth the data before sampling the mapping procedure.
- Sampling of SLA: every other data point from the SLA profiles filtered at 35 km to create super-observations.
- Mapping of SLA (MSLA): sub-optimal space and time objective analysis to map the super-observations on to a grid (0.2 degrees in longitude, 0.1 in latitude) using appropriate altimetric data error statistics (10% T/P, 15% ERS) and appropriate correlation scales (15 days - 90 km). Long wavelength errors are also removed (residual orbit error, tide and inverse barometer errors). Mapping errors are also estimated as results of the method used for the mapping.
- Produce SLA derived geostrophic velocity anomalies (GVELA) perpendicular to the track.
- Produce maps of the distribution of eddy kinetic energy ($EKE=1/2[\langle u_g'^2 \rangle + \langle v_g'^2 \rangle]$)

The maps will then be deposited in the Fugro GEOS Data Warehouse in agreed format and map projection. The altimeter results will be delivered to customers as a stand-alone product or in combination with results from in situ current measurements. The observed current measurements in one or several positions will also serve as validation data for the altimetric products.

A technical summary of the service elements is given in Table 8.

Table 8. Summary of the service elements of historical altimetric maps

Service elements	Example of product: Eddy kinetic energy maps
Responsible institution	CLS
Production chain established	yes
Example of products presented in the report	Fig. 19 and 20
Inclusion of ENVISAT data	when RA-2 data is available
Geographical coverage	Regional products from existing archived global data sets
Near real time delivery	Not relevant
Product interval	As agreed with customer
Time averaged products	Monthly, seasonal and interannual products
Product format	A standard format for raster files
Delivery of product to FG	By ftp to Data Warehouse
Reliability of product access	Good because data archives exist and will be expanded by ENVISAT and JASON data from 2002
Limiting factors of the EO product	The product is statistical and need to be compared with other similar products
Have products been used or tested by FG before ?	no
Have products been used or tested by end users before ?	yes
FG access to products from CLS	Direct delivery from CLS to FG Data Warehouse
Plan for service trial in Phase 2	No, results from previous analysis in Northwest Europe will be used in marketing and promotion.
Validation of products	Validation of the eddy kinetic energy maps will be done by comparison with in situ current measurements and with model simulations
Integration of products in a service	FG will do integration of the products as part of their services to the offshore industry.

3.2.3 Actions to be done before introduction of service to the market

Data acquisition from JASON and ENVISAT RA-2

CLS is ready to insert into the service chain new radar altimeter data from JASON in August 2002 and from ENVISAT RA-2 during the second half of 2002. New altimeters will be important for continuation of more than 10 years of global RA data.

Test area for service demonstration

The test area for service demonstration will be Northwest Europe (as shown in Fig. 18) coordinated with the service trial in the Faroe Island – Shetland area.

Validation and assessment of product

It is necessary to validate the eddy kinetic energy product against in situ measurements before the product is introduced to the market.

4. PLAN FOR SERVICES USING MODELS FOR HINDCAST AND FORECAST

The pre-operational ocean monitoring and forecasting system at NERSC consists of a physical ocean model (HYCOM), which is coupled to a dynamic and thermodynamic sea-ice model, and a marine ecosystem model. This system, which is presently running in real time for the North Atlantic within the EU-funded DIADEM and TOPAZ projects, is forced using atmospheric data obtained from European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecast (ECMWF). Sea Surface Temperature (SST) and Sea Level Anomaly (SLA) data from satellites are assimilated weekly using the Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF). This system is under development to provide two types of services for the offshore industry: 1) hindcast simulations and 2) forecasting of oceanographic variables (current, temperature, salinity, etc.). The hindcast data from every model grid point is used to calculate statistics of currents. This is then compared with statistics of currents. This is then compared with statistics from current measurements. Model simulations used in combination with observed current data is a cost-effective tool for estimation of extreme criteria for deep water construction. Forecasting is provided by the same model system when run in real time using the assimilation of weekly SST and SLA fields and forced by atmospheric forecast fields. The status and plans for development of these two service modes is discussed in this chapter.

4.1 Input data to the model system

4.1.1 Atmospheric Forcing Data

The ocean model system uses analysed and forecast atmospheric data from ECMWF as forcing fields. The data are downloaded by ftp from the ECMWF server to NERSC and are processed to the format used by the HYCOM model.

4.1.2 Remote Sensing Data

Two products from EO data are used as input to the modelling services: Sea Level Anomalies (SLA) and Sea Surface Temperature (SST) fields for the whole model area are prepared and delivered to NERSC by CLS once per week. The SLA and SST fields presently delivered by CLS are provided in a format ready for use in the data assimilation system

Additional work will include:

- development of data inversion algorithms for ENVISAT data to produce SLA and SST fields, which can be assimilated into the ocean model
- development of combined parameters from the diagnostic model states, which can be more easily related to parameters observed by remote sensing data

4.1.3 In situ data

The ocean modelling system is designed to include assimilation schemes for point measurements/profiles of temperature and salinity. Current measurements from fixed current meters and ADCPs could in principle be assimilated into the modelling system. However, since

currents are driven by wind and thermohaline circulation, it is not a well-posed problem to assimilate current data directly into the model. Instead, current data will be used for validation of model results. Instead, current data will be used for validation of model results. In situ data for assimilation will therefore be temperature and salinity and particularly those collected through the ARGO program which are available for CLS through the French Coriolis server.

4.2 Plan for a model-based hindcast service

Offshore industry requires good knowledge of ocean processes for optimal rig selection in the design phase. When starting development in new areas it is common to deploy current meter moorings to measure current statistics, and in particular to find extreme situations which is among the most important of metocean criteria. In addition to current measurements, it is planned to establish a new service, which provides a hindcast simulation from regional high resolution models which are nested to a coarser –resolution model on global scale. The model system must be tuned to observed-data in order to produce statistics, which are in agreement with observations. The active elements of the service chain are shown in Fig. 21.

Figure 21. Active components of the service chain in the case of model hindcast simulations

4.2.1 Existing model system

A model system has been established by NERSC for the European Atlantic margin, called the NWAG model with three nested models on different scales and resolution (Fig. 22a). It has been developed for use in hindcast mode and will be further developed for use in forecast mode. Diadem3H is the large scale coarser model covering the whole Atlantic and Arctic, Nsea3H is an intermediate model defined for an area including all of the North Sea and the Atlantic Margin using a model resolution of 7 km and NwagH with 2 km resolution is set up to ensure a good representation of the mesoscale variability in the core study area northwest of Scotland (Fig. 22 b). This is a typical example of how the high resolution model is set up including the use of intermediate models.

Figure 22. a) Nesting of two regional models onto the global Diadem3H model; b) example of simulations by the 2 km NwagH model

Details of the NwagH model simulations in the Faroe Island - Shetland - Orkney Islands regions are shown in Fig 23a, while a vertical section of the DiademH model across the Iceland – Scotland ridge is shown in Fig. 23b. Hindcast simulations with the NWAG model system has been run for 15 months (1996 – 1997) and validation of model performance has been performed using current measurements to ensure that model data give similar current statistics to the observed data. An

example of such validation, using data from a current meter mooring in the Faroe Shetland channel is shown in Fig. 24 where exceedence plots of the two data sets are presented.

Figure 23. a) Subset of the output from the *NwagH* model showing surface temperature and current at a given time; b) is a subset of a temperature vertical section from the *Diadem3H* coarse resolution model across the Iceland-Scotland ridge.

Figure 24. Example of NWAG model simulations compared with current measurements in the Faroe-Shetland Channel where the maximum current is found near the bottom.

The complete data set of modelled oceanographic parameters, such as current, temperature, salinity, has been provided to Fugro GEOS for further analysis and retrieval of statistics as required by the customers. The data set is about 32 Gbyte per year, covering 9146 grid points at one hour time resolution. NERSC, who have produced these data as part of the NWAG project, has delivered the data set to FG, who will use it to develop more products for supporting the offshore industry operating in the NWAG area. A summary of the service elements is given in Table 9.

Table 9. Summary of the service elements of model-based hindcast

Service elements	Products: Data set of modelled current in every grid point for a given period. From this data set, a number of different derived products can be estimated
Responsible institution	NERSC and FG
Production chain established	Yes, for the Northwest European margin. For other regions, high resolution model simulations need to be provided before the service can deliver products.
Example of products presented in the report	Fig. 22, 23 and 24
Inclusion of ENVISAT data	Altimeter data, including ENVISAT, can have a role as validation data sets for the current products
Geographical coverage	Regional products exist for Northwest Europe
Near real time delivery	Not relevant
Product interval	As agreed with customer
Time averaged products	Full flexibility to calculate time averaged products
Product format	A standard format for raster files
Delivery of product to FG	By ftp to Data Warehouse
Reliability of product access	Good because model simulations have to be established before the service can start to deliver products
Limiting factors of the EO product	EO data are not used as direct input to the model products, but can have a role in validation.
Have products been used or tested by FG before ?	yes
Have products been used or tested by end users before ?	yes
FG access to products from NERSC	Direct delivery from NERSC to FG Data Warehouse
Plan for service development in Phase 2	In Northwest Europe
Validation of products	Validation of the model simulations maps will be done as an extension of the NWAG project by comparison with in situ current measurements.
Integration of products in a service	FG will do integration of the products as part of their services to the offshore industry.

4.2.2 Actions for further development of hindcast service

Clarify property issues of the NWAG data proposed to be used.

The NWAG group has exclusive rights to the model data collected in the UK sector, while NERSC and Fugro Geos hold the exclusive rights to the model data in the Faroes and Irish sectors.

Products can be derived and presented to the NWAG members through the EMOFOR project using all the data, but a permission is required before any of the modelled or observed data from the UK sector can be promoted to non NWAG members.

Use of existing hindcast data to make more products for the service trial

There will be no new generation of hindcast data in this project. The service trial will use the existing data set for the Faroe-Shetland area to develop additional products such as products of extreme current statistics. For example may current exceedence plots be delivered for any of the stored model every grid cell. This will be a task for FG.

Hindcast data in a database

To facilitate retrieval and further analysis of the hindcast data, they are currently included in a database, which will become accessible via Internet. This is a joint effort between NERSC and FG.

Preparation of products for promotion in Phase 2

Examples of more products derived from the hindcast data set will be prepared by FG during Phase 2. Additional products will be defined and prepared for the service promotion as part of EMOFOR Task 4 (Achieve market acceptance). This is a joint effort between NERSC and FG.

Use of in situ measurements for validation of hindcast model data

The hindcast current estimates can be compared against in situ measurements at sites where such data exist. Example of such comparison is shown in Fig. 27. This comparison will be useful for validation of the model in specific areas where the model accuracy is important.

Figure 27. Example of comparison of current statistics at a given site in the Faroe Island region from (a) in situ measurements and (b) model simulations.

Use of EO data as part of the validation of the hindcast data.

Eddy statistics from altimeter hindcast data, in form of eddy kinetic energy maps or other related parameters, will be compared with similar parameters derived from model hindcast data set. It is not feasible to compare each eddy from the model simulations with coincident eddy information from satellite data, because a model which is unconstrained by observations will develop its own meso-scale variability and thus not be able to reproduce individual eddies observed in the data. However, in a statistical sense it is possible to compare the two data sets and assess the regional and seasonal variability in eddy activity. This is a joint effort between NERSC, CLS and FG.

4.3 Plan to develop a model-based forecasting service.

Forecasting of metocean conditions is important to support decisions associated with critical operations and to take precautions if severe conditions are anticipated, for example if a strong eddy current is approaching an offshore installation. The active components of the service chain in the forecasting mode are shown in Figure. 28.

Figure 28. Active components of the service chain in the case of model forecasting

Forecasting of currents must be capable of resolving mesoscale dynamics for a prediction period of 1 – 7 days. The forecasting system needs to use high-resolution models of the target area nested within large-scale models. The forecasting models also need to assimilate observational data available in near real-time.

4.3.1 Status of existing forecasting service

The forecasting service at NERSC is being developed as a continuation of the hindcast model system. The tuning and validation of model performance is a critical element before a model system can be used for prediction. Much of this tuning and validation has been done as part of the hindcast analysis carried out in the Faroe-Shetland region. Since October 2000 the DIADEM /TOPAZ ocean forecasting system has been operated for the whole Atlantic, the Nordic Seas and the Arctic using the assimilation scheme shown in Fig. 29. The basic idea of data assimilation is that an improved estimate can be obtained by combining observation and model data in a systematic manner using proper error statistics for the observed data and model prediction.

Figure 29. Scheme for assimilation of SLA and SST into the DIADEM/TOPAZ system

The assimilation methodology used is a version of the Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF) developed at NERSC. The method is similar to a traditional Kalman Filter but specifically designed to handle large state spaces and highly nonlinear dynamics which are characteristics of high resolution ocean general circulation models. The EnKF adopts an ensemble of model states for representing error statistics and evolves the error statistics in time by forward integration of each individual ensemble member. The analysis scheme operates directly on the ensemble and provides an efficient methodology to compute the analysis. The EnKF has been derived from basic mathematical principles and therefore provides a consistent solution to the assimilation problem.

Satellite remote sensing data such as sea surface temperature and sea level anomalies fields are routinely assimilated into the forecasting system. The SLA data are currently available as gridded fields with a 7 days delay compared to real time.

The real time assimilation procedure goes as follows: The satellite data fields are delivered by CLS once per week with a 7 days delay. The EnKF analysis is computed for this day as soon as the data has arrived at NERSC. The updated or analyzed ensemble of model state is then integrated forward in time for one week to produce a nowcast. During this integration the model uses analyzed atmospheric forcing data from ECMWF. Thereafter a single model is initialized using the ensemble mean nowcast (which is the best estimate of the ocean state) and integrated 7 days into the future to make a forecast while forced by atmospheric forecast data also obtained from ECMWF.

Results from the monitoring and forecasting system is currently presented on the web, but full data files (6 Gbyte each in the TOPAZ model system) are stored in the NERSC computer system. Result files will be delivered to the FG Data Warehouse.

An example of results from the DIADEM/TOPAZ system are shown in Fig. 30, where surface height and surface current are shown in a) for a given time. The Gulf Stream system with meanders and rings being generated east of 70°W are predicted quite well. The meanders and rings have dimensions of 200 – 300 km or more and are therefore resolvable with the grid cells of the model. To quantify the accuracy of the prediction, the difference in SSH between model results and data from altimeter is shown in b). The largest discrepancies in SSH are found in the area of the Gulf Stream rings and meanders. Finally, when SSH data are assimilated into the model, the difference between model and data becomes smaller, as shown in c). These differences are also in good agreement with the predicted errors from the EnKF. The service elements are summarized in Table 10.

Figure 30. a) Example of forecast of Northeast Atlantic using the DIADEM/TOPAZ system;
b) Difference in SSH between model forecast and altimeter data; and
c) The same difference after use of assimilation.

Table 10. Summary of the service elements of the forecasting service

Service elements	Example of product: 1 – 7 day forecast of currents in all grid points of the model area
Responsible institution	NERSC
Production chain established	Yes, for the Northwest European margin. For other regions, high resolution model simulations need to be provided before the service can deliver products.
Example of products presented in the report	Fig. 30 and 31
Inclusion of ENVISAT data	Altimeter data (SLA) and SST, including ENVISAT, are used for assimilation in the model
Geographical coverage	Regional products exist for Northwest Europe and Gulf of Mexico
Near real time delivery	yes
Product interval	As agreed with customer, for Gulf of Mexico proposed interval is 7 days
Time averaged products	Full flexibility to calculate time averaged products
Product format	A standard format for raster files
Delivery of product to FG	By ftp to Data Warehouse
Reliability of product access	Good because model simulations have to be established and tested before the service can start to deliver products
Limiting factors of the EO product	EO data are used for assimilation in the service. The sensibility of EO products in the overall service is not established.
Have products been used or tested by FG before ?	yes
Have products been used or tested by end users before ?	yes
FG access to products from NERSC	Direct delivery from NERSC to FG Data Warehouse
Plan for service trial in Phase 2	In Northwest Europe and Gulf of Mexico (see description in chapter 6)
Validation of products	Validation of the model simulations will be done as part of the service trials, by comparison with in situ current measurements.
Integration of products in a service	FG will do integration of the products as part of their services to the offshore industry. This will be tested during as part of the service trials

4.3.2 Actions required to establish high resolution forecasting service in specific regions

The approach to develop a regional forecasting system for the offshore industry is to

- Nest a high-resolution model (also based on HYCOM) covering the target region to a coarser basin scale system (DIADEM/TOPAZ)
- Use sophisticated assimilation methods, i.e. EnKF and EnOI, to assimilate data from satellites and in situ observing systems in the regional model,

In the context of EMOFOR the plan is to set up and run regional forecasting as one of the service trials. The planned area for testing regional forecasting is the Gulf of Mexico. The main work tasks carried out at NERSC in 2002 to prepare for this forecasting trial are

Task 1. Define time cycles of the monitoring/forecasting for the Gulf of Mexico

- Obtain an environmental overview of the area and determine processes to be forecasted
- Select time cycles in the monitoring and forecasting system to resolve typical processes

Task 2. Model coverage and grid.

- Determine the model grid for the large-scale model and the nested high-resolution model, taking into account location of in situ current moorings, which can provide validation data.
- Set up the high resolution model nested with the large-scale model

Task 3. Prepare for assimilation of data into the forecasting system

- SST and SLA data will be assimilated into the large scale model as before, but with new data from ENVISAT and JASON contributing to the SST and SLA fields.
- Plan assimilation of available in situ data and decide if the data are useful for assimilation or should be used for validation only.
- Prepare for assimilation into the regional model using Ensemble OI.

Task 4. Testing and adjustments of the forecasting system.

- Carry out test runs of the forecasting system.
- Compare output from the test runs by comparing the results with in situ measurements and EO data.
- Interact with customers to make sure that the system will meet their requirements
- Make necessary adjustments of the system.
- Prepare for the service trial experiment, including delivery of products to FG Data Warehouse

Task 5: Clarify usage of atmospheric forcing data for the forecasting service

- Two candidate providers of global atmospheric forcing data are ECMWF and NCEP. The terms for use of their atmospheric data for commercial services need to be defined.
- If needed, other providers need to be contacted to define their prices for atmospheric data.

Task 6: Implementation of service trial experiment (described in Chapter 6).

5. DATA PROCUREMENT PLAN

Data planned to be used in the project include visible, infrared and microwave data. For eddy monitoring the basic products will be water quality parameters (chlorophyll and sediment concentration) from ocean colour sensors, sea surface temperature from thermal infrared sensors, medium to high resolution SAR data, and sea level anomalies derived from altimeter data. These data are available from different sensors, and through different services worldwide. These services may have different levels of operability, ranging from purely investigation and scientific data sets to near real-time operational data provision. Because the focus of this proposal is market development, a high level of operational use (reliability, rapidity, accuracy, sustainability) is required. Hereafter, we will thus provide some details on the main providers, services and prices (when available) related to the current and near-to-come earth observation data under consideration.

5.1 Use of ENVISAT data

The operational services developed in EMOFOR will use data from more than one satellite system for several reasons:

- secure continuous access to EO data (if one satellite fails others can deliver data)
- increase the amount of data that can be used, especially increasing the temporal and spatial coverage is important for services to the offshore industry
- improve the accuracy and quality of the products derived from the EO data by combining information from several satellites and sensors (synergy of data). Synergistic use of data from several satellites to obtain better spatial/temporal coverage and quality of products is in development. With ENVISAT, such synergetic use will be further developed.

For this project, altimeter data from ENVISAT will be used in combination with Topex/Poseidon and JASON data. ASAR data from ENVISAT will be used together with RADARSAT, and MERIS data will be used instead of VEGETATION. AATSR-SST data will be used instead of AVHRR.

With the successful launch of ENVISAT in March this year, the plan is to have the first examples of products available from RA-2, ASAR and MERIS during the second half of 2002. ENVISAT data will be available through the EOLI catalogue service (<http://odisseo.esrin.esa.it/eoli>), but the near-real-time delivery of data is not yet clear.

The first MERIS/ASAR data sets ordered by NERSC covers the coastal waters of Norway in connection with a validation experiment in May – June 2002. These data have not yet been delivered by ESA. MERIS/ASAR data will primarily be used for mapping eddies and other ocean surface features in near real time, as shown in Table 6. RA-2 data will be used to provide a more quantitative estimate of eddies and other current phenomena. It is planned to have examples of synergistic products from ENVISAT and other satellites available by the end of 2002.

CLS has developed a processing system for the measurements provided by the AVHRR infrared radiometer on board the NOAA satellites in order to generate sea surface temperature maps.

AVHRR is a key EO source for SST products, often for historical reasons (flying on the series of NOAA satellites used for the operational meteorology mission). ENVISAT AASTR will be used to enhance SST product accuracy for scientific applications and to explore a combination with AVHRR based SST products. ATS-NR-2P (gridded surface temperature) products offer for example 1-km resolution and are specified with an accuracy < 0.3 °C.

CLS has also developed a processing system, which produces high-resolution water-colour maps using the measurements from Vegetation, a radiometer, which works in the visible/NIR spectrum on board the SPOT series. These data will also be available for the eddy tracking service.

MERIS Reduced Resolution Level 2P products will be generated systematically by ENVISAT Ground Segment. Product accuracy is specified as $< 15\%$ for chlorophyll retrieval, $< 30\%$ for yellow substance and $< 15\%$ for suspended matter. Absolute accuracy is of little concern for applications such as eddy tracking. Actually a simple RGB colour composite of three spectral bands in the visible would in most cases be sufficient for the detection of eddies. Such products can be obtained from a number of 1-km resolution sensors such as AVHRR, SeaWiFS, MODIS, and VEGETATION. However more advanced products such as maps of chlorophyll and sediment concentration (considered as tracers of water masses) may provide more detailed information on fronts, and meso-scale circulation features.

Table 11 summarises the differences between Vegetation and MERIS.

Table 11. Characteristics of MERIS and VEGETATION

Satellite geometry	MERIS RR	VEGETATION
Orbit	35 days cycle	26 days cycle
Swath	1150 km	2250km
Pixel size	1,2 km	1,25 km
Spectral bands	15	4

For eddy monitoring trials, the plan is to use these AASTR and MERIS RR level 2 products as input to IR and optical eddy maps. AVHRR and VEGETATION data would be used as backup.

5.2 SAR data acquisition

The two main sources of SAR data currently available are the European Space Agency and the Canadian company Radarsat Inc.

ESA's SAR data are available through the main ESA ordering board at ESRIN (<http://earthnet.esrin.esa.it>). The data archive can be browsed using the free DESCW software provided by ESA or the new EOLI online multi-mission catalogue and ordering service at ESA facility (<http://odisseo.esrin.esa.it/eoli>). ENVISAT-ASAR will be available through the earthnet web-site (see above). ASAR data can be available worldwide due to the recording device onboard

ENVISAT. ASAR data for this project will be ordered for the selected study areas. Near real-time delivery will be an important element of the SAR data provision. Archive browsing will be made possible using the DESCW software.

Action: The costs of data and products from ASAR for commercial services must be defined by ESA.

RADARSAT-SAR data are available from Radarsat Inc. (<http://www.rsi.ca>). The satellite must be programmed to acquire data, which implies that no real-time or immediate provision of data can be ensured. Several programming options are available to respond to a range of operational requirements. Average price is 5,400 Euro per scene (half price for data acquired before 1999). Discounts are also available for ordering of more than 25 scenes per year. For the selection of frames a *Swath Planner Application* (SPA) software is available. It is not freeware or public domain software. Image requests should be submitted four weeks before the planned acquisition date. Processing and delivery for the main products is approximately two weeks after image acquisition. In general data are delivered by courier, on data cartridges or CD-ROM. Data for this project need to be delivered in near real time.

5.3 Acquisition of infrared radiometer and spectrometer data

Cloud cover and haze prevents use of the optical satellite sensors to observe the surface of the earth regularly. Hence, the nominal “daily coverage” achieved especially at high latitudes may in reality become significantly less. The availability of cloud free data varies significantly with season and geographic location. Because of erratic cloud conditions, it may be difficult to regularly monitor eddies by the sole mean of optical data. It is then appropriate to integrate EO information from several passes (days) as well as to use data from radar systems (SAR and altimeter), which are independent on cloud cover.

Thermal-IR data

Operational provision of sea surface temperature (SST) from thermal infrared sensors is currently available from the US NOAA AVHRR sensors and the ESA ERS-2-ATSR. Other SST data are available from the US MODIS sensor on the Terra satellite. ENVISAT AASTR will be used to enhance SST products and contribute to SST global fields.

Action: Clarification of costs and near real-time access to ATSR-NR-2P (gridded surface temperature) product for commercial services must be done by ESA.

Ocean colour data

At present, ocean colour data are available by not less than ten different sensors from seven different countries (see <http://www.ioccg.org/500m.html> for details on sensors). However SeaWiFS is currently the only one amongst these sensors dedicated to ocean colour measurement which can provide data with a level of reliability acceptable for operational use.

Vegetation Instrument (VGT)

The *Végétation* instrument is on-board the SPOT-4 and SPOT-5 satellites. It is composed of 4 cameras, each of them composed of a wide field-of-view optic with telecentric lens, a spectral band and an acquisition line of 1728 detectors. The total field-of-view is 101° cross track leading to a ground swath of 2250 km and the ground resolution of about 1km at nadir is almost constant over the entire field-of-view. The four complementary spectral bands are the blue band (B0 from 0.43 to 0.57 μm), the red band (B2 from 0.61 to 0.68 μm), the near-infrared band (B3 from 0.79 to 0.89 μm), and the short-wave infrared band (SWIR from 1.58 to 1.75 μm). The blue band was defined primarily for atmospheric correction.

Unlike SeaWiFS, *Végétation* was not designed for ocean color measurements. *Végétation*, however, offers global data acquisition and a fully operational ground segment delivering timely products. It has been demonstrated in Fournies et al. (2001) that ocean color measurements can be deduced from the *Végétation* blue band.

Medium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer (MERIS)

MERIS offers significant advantages over current ocean colour satellites including:

- Spectral bands: MERIS has 15 wavebands that can be programmed in width and location, which means that specific channels could be modified to observe specific phenomena e.g. red tides,
- Spatial resolution: MERIS has two spatial resolution modes – 300 metre regionally (Full Resolution) and 1.2 km globally (Reduced Resolution); The better spatial resolution (300 meters) will make it better suited for use in coastal and fjord studies,
- Radiometric resolution: data are digitised to 16 bits and the S/N ratios are very high (noise equivalent radiance of below 0.033 $\text{W m}^{-2} \text{sr}^{-1} \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ in the visible and 0.025 in the NIR),
- Calibration: MERIS has a number of on-board calibration mechanisms to measure potential system response degradation and wavelength stability of the sensor,
- Synergy with other instruments: the ENVISAT satellite will carry a suite of instruments, which will enable simultaneous observation of ocean colour, sea-surface temperature, surface elevation and surface roughness, by sensors partly covering the same swath. This will enable the ocean colour biological information to be tied more closely to physical structures of the oceans.

A disadvantage of MERIS is that it does not tilt away from the sun and so images will be affected by sun glint, which may affect observations when the area of interest is on the eastern part of the sensor swath.

MERIS data will be accessed via two main routes:

- Pre-operational research requirements are classified at Category 1 and will be supported directly from ESA User Services.

- Operational applications, so-called Category 2, will obtain data through ESA delegated “distribution entities”.

Access to EO data in near-real time is crucial for operational service and ESA quotes the delivery of Fast Delivery (FD) products at three hours for the low-resolution products; high resolution, including presumably MERIS-FR will be processed upon request and may take 1-3 days to deliver.

Action: Clarification of costs and near real-time delivery of MERIS data for commercial services must be done by ESA

5.4 Radar altimeter data

CLS will provide all radar altimeter data and products derived from these data to the EMOFOR services, including RA2 data.

Action: The costs of RA2 data and products for commercial services must be defined by ESA

5.5 Other data

In situ data will be provided by Fugro GEOS, while atmospheric forcing data will be obtained from NCEP or ECMWF. Climatological oceanographic data will be provided by NERSC.

5.6 Concluding remarks and key issues related to EO data

ESA’s ENVISAT offers possibly the best combination of sensors in terms of flexibility and capability for operational eddy tracking, however near-real-time access to data is not yet defined and may be a limiting factor for some of the service elements. Although a price and distribution policy has been defined by ESA, no formal information on products price (for commercial applications) and near real-time delivery has yet been disclosed. This is a very critical point for services to the offshore industry. Successful services for this market can only be established if the cost-benefit is clearly demonstrated. This will be a main objective for the service trials planned for Phase 2 of EMOFOR.

6. PLAN FOR SERVICE TRIALS

The two proposed service scenarios to be implemented and demonstrated in Phase 2 of EMOFOR are:

- Eddy mapping and tracking with EO data in near real time
- Forecasting using models and data assimilation

The service trials will be set up for specific regions where Fugro GEOS and the offshore industry are active and there is a potential market for the services. The location of the service trials are summarised in Table 12.

Table 12. Location of service trials

Service scenario	Planned areas for service trials		
	Monitoring mode (near real time)	Hindcast mode (statistics from time series)	Forecasting mode (1 – 7 days)
1 Eddy mapping and tracking with EO data	Gulf of Mexico Northwest Europe		
2 Eddy statistics from altimeter hindcast data		No specific service trial	
3 Statistics from model hindcast data		No specific service trial	
4 Forecasting using models and data assimilation			Gulf of Mexico

Customers of Fugro GEOS will be involved in the detailed planning and implementation of the service trials and for evaluation of the results of the service trials, which are planned to be completed by the end of 2003.

6.1 Eddy tracking using EO data

6.1.1 Area

It is planned to carry out eddy tracking service trials in two different regions where deepwater development is going on and oceanographic processes and met-ocean conditions are different. This will require that the EMOFOR service can be adapted to given conditions in any ocean region.

- 1) In Northwest Europe where the inflow of the North-Atlantic Current generates eddies along self breaks where several deep water exploration areas are under development. The eddies are frequently found in the inflow of Atlantic water through the Faroe-Shetland Channel,

propagating into the Norwegian Sea. The eddies are developing fairly quickly and propagate to the northeast. Due to frequent cloud cover, optical and IR images have limited usefulness, whereas altimeter and SAR can deliver more regular information.

- 2) In the Gulf of Mexico where the dominant processes of importance for deep water operations are Loop Current eddies (Fig 31), sub-surface jets and near bed intensification of currents. The Loop Current eddies have long lifetime (several months) and they are shed off typically one per year. They are well suited for observations by satellite data, both altimeter, optical and IR images.

6.1.2 Data acquisition and product preparation

The two different regions are chosen because the character of the eddies is different and the detection capability can be tested under different met-ocean conditions. The frequency of observation is determined by the propagation speed which is relatively high in Northwest Europe and relatively slow in the Gulf of Mexico. For both regions, altimeter SLA maps will be produced at an interval from 2 – 7 days, depending on quickly the eddies move. Infrared and optical images from MERIS/ASAR/AATSR used in synergy with NOAA AVHRR and other satellite data will be acquired and used in near real time (i.e. within 1 day) to identify and monitor the propagation of the eddies. Under cloudfree conditions IR and optical images will be used, while SAR will be used under cloudy conditions. Northwest Europe will have more cloudy days than the Gulf of Mexico, indicating that SAR data will be more useful in the latter area.

Figure 31. a) Map of Gulf of Mexico showing the main current pattern including the loop eddies; b) example of Mean Sea level Anomaly and Geostrophic Velocity Map showing the eddies present on 8 May 2002.

Figure 32. a) Map of the Faroe Islands – Scotland area where service trials are planned using IR images (b), optical images or SAR images as appropriate. Sea Level Anomaly and Geostrophic velocity maps will also be delivered as shown in c) for 8 May 2002 and d) 15 May 2002.

6.1.3 Timing of service trial and involvement of customers

The eddy tracking service trials in the two regions will be carried out during 2003. Customer who are working actively in offshore development in Northwest Europe and in Gulf of Mexico will be involved in the planning and implementation of the service trials as receivers of the products to be delivered. The timing of the service trials will be done in agreement with the customer. In Northwest Europe the service trial will be relatively short, tentatively 2 – 3 weeks with intense, daily delivery of products to a selected customer. In the Gulf of Mexico, where eddy life time is

longer and advection is slower compared to Northwest Europe, the service trial will last for several months and with delivery of EO products tentatively once per week. Example of eddies observed in IR images (Fig. 32 b) and rapid changes in eddies in weekly altimeter-derived maps are shown in Fig. 32 c,d.

6.1.4 Calculation of service cost

The service trials will be used to calculate the costs of delivering the EO products to a customer. For each of the four products (Altimeter SLA maps, SAR eddy maps, IR eddy maps and optical eddy maps) the main cost factors are:

- Data costs for commercial use of altimeter, SAR, optical and infrared images from data providers
- Processing cost for CLS and NERSC to prepare products
- Costs for Fugro GEOS to integrate, present and distribute the information products

6.1.5 Evaluation and assessment of products

After the service trials have been completed, Fugro GEOS in co-operation with the involved customers will evaluate and assess the service products. Identification of critical elements and improvements to be implemented before moving to full operational service. Carry out a market review among a wider group of customers.

6.2 Forecasting using models and data assimilation

A model-based forecasting service for met-ocean conditions is under development at NERSC and will be included as part of the EMOFOR services. The data flow and technical description of this service is described in chapter 4.3. The service will be demonstrated as a real time monitoring and forecasting experiment is planned to be carried out in an area where the model is set up with high resolution, nested to the Diadem3H global model.

6.2.1 Area, products and timing

The selected area for the service trial will be the Gulf of Mexico where characteristic eddies and loop currents represent the maximum currents which need to be monitored and forecasted for deep sea operations. The forecasting service trial will be co-ordinated with the eddy detection trial described in chapter 6.1. An example of output from the high-resolution model that NERSC has set up and tested in the Gulf of Mexico is shown in Fig. 33.

It is noteworthy that the model can simulate very similar eddies as observed in the altimeter products. Preliminary model simulations as well as altimeter analysis show that the eddies in the Gulf of Mexico can persist for many months. The altimeter products which show updated MSLA and geostrophic currents every 7 days in May 2002 (Fig. 34) indicate a dominant cyclonic eddy in the eastern part (violet) and an anti-cyclonic eddy (red) in the western part of the Gulf in this

period. Over a period of one month the eddies are fairly stable although they may change their shape, size and position.

Figure 33. Example of sea surface temperature and surface current pattern produced by a high-resolution model in the Gulf of Mexico

Figure 34. Current maps from altimeter data for a period of 7 days in (a) the first week and (b) the last week of May 2002, showing cyclonic and anti-cyclonic eddies in the Gulf of Mexico.

The service trials will be carried out over several months in the first 6 – 9 months of 2003. The forecast will be carried out for 7 days and be repeated at the same interval. Altimetric MSLA and SST products will be used for assimilation, as described in chapter 4.3. A key customer will be involved in the planning and implementation of the service trial. Locations where long-term in situ measurements exist will be used for validation of the forecasting. Eddy maps from SST, optical images and SAR will also be used for validation of the model output.

6.2.2 Cost estimates

The service trials will be used to calculate the costs of delivering the 7-day forecasts for the Gulf of Mexico to a customer. The main cost factors are:

- The cost of setting up and running the model system for a specified region and period
- The cost of validating model performance against in situ data and satellite data
- The costs of running the model in real time with data assimilation and delivering forecast products
- The costs to integrate, present and distribute the information products to customers

6.2.3 Evaluation and assessment of the forecasting

During the months when the service trial is run, Fugro GEOS in co-operation with the involved customers will evaluate and assess the forecasting products. In situ measurements as well as satellite eddy tracking maps will be used in the evaluation. By the end of the service trial period, an assessment of the forecasting system will be done in co-operation with the key customers who have received the products during the service trials.

6.3.4 Promotion and marketing

Due to the very competitive market for met-ocean services in the Gulf of Mexico, the promotion and marketing of the forecasting service will be carefully planned by FG during the first 6 – 9 months of 2003.

7. SUMMARY OF ACTIONS FOR THE SERVICE DEVELOPMENT

7.1 Cost of services

The cost of services is being estimated and is reported in D2/D10 Consolidated Business Plan. The service trials will be used to calculate the overall cost of delivering the proposed service modes. When the market review is going to be performed (as part of task 4), cost versus benefit of the service modes will be assessed based on feedback from the strategic customers.

7.2 Cost of EO data

A major unknown factor is the commercial price for some of the EO data, especially ENVISAT data. It is essential to establish the commercial prices for use of ENVISAT (and other EO-data) in order to calculate the overall cost of the service modes. For example, the commercial price of SAR images to be used in eddy tracking represent the largest cost factor of EO data for the eddy tracking service. Commercial price for RADARSAT data is 3000 USD per ScanSAR scene, while preliminary price of ENVISAT ASAR Wideswath scene is 1500 Euro. The service trials and the market assessment will be used to assess if and under what conditions SAR data are cost-effective for the customers. Use of SAR data will be balanced against use of less expensive altimetry and optical/IR images.

7.3 Involvement of a key customer in the service trials

Fugro GEOS has started the process of selecting a key customer for each of the two areas where the service trials are planned. In the Gulf of Mexico Shell will be the key customer, while in Northwest Europe it will be BP. The key customers will participate in the planning and implementation of the service trials, including definition of the products, contents and layout of the products, timing and delivery, etc.

7.4 Clarification of limitations and advantages of the proposed EO-based products

All information sources on met-ocean conditions have limitations as well as advantages of technical character that must be clearly stated prior to the service trials. Not all the limitations are necessarily known prior the service trials. However, the service trials will be important to define these limitations before marketing of the service will start.

7.5 Assessment of service trials

After the service trials, described in chapter 6, have been completed and their cost estimated, a market assessment will be performed where several customers will receive the results of the trials and give feedback on technical quality and cost. This will be used in assessment of further service viability.

7.6 Further marketing and promotion activities

A plan for marketing and promotion activities will be prepared by Fugro GEOS in parallel with the service trials, taking into account that the market is very competitive and correct timing and contents of the marketing efforts will be critical for further development of the service.